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The **Jews** of Thessaloniki:

**Legacies of the Past,
Shaping of Traditions,**

Challenges for the Future

Paul Isaac Hagouel, Ph.D.

paul231011@berkeley.edu

Athens, October 5, 2017

The Holocaust: Diachronic and Interdisciplinary Approaches

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paul231011@berkeley.edu

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Paper

The Jews of Thessaloniki: Legacies of the Past, Shaping of Traditions, Challenges for the Future

Paul Isaac Hagouel¹

Ladies and Gentlemen

I take this opportunity to thank Professor **Sotirios Despotis** for his kind invitation to the Conference and to salute the 180th anniversary since the founding of the National & Kapodistrian University of Athens. I also thank Dr. **Efstathios Lianos Liantis**, Special Secretary for Religious and Cultural Diplomacy & Head of the Greek Delegation to the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance for his support.

Abstract

More than 2 millennia of Jewish presence in Thessaloniki have shaped both the city and its Jews. The Jews of Thessaloniki, in most instances, were subject to the fortunes and misfortunes of their coreligionists in the realms of the Kingdom of Macedonia, the Roman Empire, the Eastern Roman Empire – Byzantium and the Ottoman Empire. A new and current chapter in their history is the birth of the modern Hellenic state and its foundation on civil rights. In the second decade of the 20th century the Jews of Thessaloniki finally belong, on equal par with the overwhelming Christian majority, as Hellenes in Greece. The tumultuous events of the previous century, both worldwide and locally, had profound consequences for Jewish Thessaloniki. Still the community is in search of its current identity and of a vision for the future. Our presence here enhances my optimism.

The history of the Jews of and in Thessaloniki is a vast topic that has been addressed by a number of historians² and researchers

¹ Paul Isaac Hagouel, 11 Chrysostomou Smyrnis Street, GR–54622 Thessaloniki, Greece, paul231011@berkeley.edu, berkeley.academia.edu/PaulIsaacHagouel

Member Greek Delegation to IHRA, Member Academic Working Group & Member Committee Genocide of the Roma, <https://holocaustremembrance.com/>

² Joseph Nehama (1880-1971), *Histoire des Israélites de Salonique*, 5 volumes published between 1935-1949. The manuscript of the 6th and 7th volumes was ready in 1940. It was published in 1978 as a single volume by the Jewish Community of Thessaloniki [JCT] KdöR [public legal entity] in 1978 (all in French). <http://www.sephardicstudies.org/nehama.html> (20170922)

Béatrice Leroy, *Joseph Nehama, Histoire des Israélites de Salonique*. [compte rendu], *Bulletin Hispanique*, Volume 81 Numéro 3 pp. 341-357, Année 1979

over the years. After all, it is inexorably linked with the history of the other people of the geographic area, spanning more than 2000 years, tumultuous historical events and 3 Empires. Even though the blow that was meted to Jewish Thessaloniki by the German Reich during the Second World War essentially wiped out Judaism in the city³, the challenges of the future of the now small, but vibrant, Jewish presence force us to build on our rich and glorious past.

Thessaloniki was founded in 315 BCE by General Kassandros who married the half-sister of Alexander the Great, of the same name, daughter of King Phillip the 2nd of the Macedonian Kingdom. Thessaloniki became part of the Roman Empire in 168 BCE. It is conjectured that the first Jews to arrive in the city were from Alexandria circa 140 BCE. It was during that same period, in 165 BCE, that the Maccabees revolted against the rule of Antiochus IV of the Seleucid Macedonians who had desecrated the Temple.⁴

Furthermore, insofar as Judaism was concerned, this was the first instance of a conqueror claiming religious supremacy in order to rule over a people – the Jews. It is interesting to note that Jews celebrate Hanukkah for the occasion and, at the same time, they tend to forget the wrath of the zealots against their brethren who, while retaining their Jewish traditions, also adopted Hellenistic

http://www.persee.fr/doc/hispa_0007-4640_1979_num_81_3_4402_t1_0341_0000_6 (20170922)

Texts by Albert Nar, *Jewish Community of Thessaloniki*, (out of print) Historical Elements [tit-bits], Greek pages 1-24 & English pages 25-48, JCT, 1992

- ³ Paul Isaac Hagouel (pdf), *The History of the Jews of Thessaloniki and the Holocaust: an Exposé* Invited Lecture at West Chester University of Pennsylvania, USA 2006 ([2013](#)) [The History of the Jews of Salonika and the Holocaust: An Exposé](#) English Presentation & Show 2006 West Chester, Penna & 2013 Sephardic Horizons <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTcDBuYzU4UC1XUWM/view?usp=sharing> <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTb3ltejJZWnFlSk0/view?usp=sharing> Presentation in Greek & show _ 2008 US Consulate General, Thessaloniki <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTUEdXVIZWTzRUYjA/view?usp=sharing> <https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTWXZJS0taMEZWb3M/view?usp=sharing>
- ⁴ Wassilis Aswestopoulos, *Griechenland _ Chanukka bei den Hellenen: Zwischen Athen und Thessaloniki begeht man das Lichterfest dieser Tage eher im Stillen*, *Jüdische Allgemeine*, Berlin, 28.11.2013 (20170922) <http://www.juedische-allgemeine.de/article/view/id/17707> Paul Isaac Hagouel (including text sent to Herr Aswestopoulos) https://www.academia.edu/5449331/Chanukka_bei_den_Hellenen_-_Zwischen_Athen_und_Thessaloniki_begeht_man_das_Lichterfest_dieser_Tage_eher_im_Stillen

customs. It is thus safe to assume that the pull of Hellenism was strong because each one (Judaism and Hellenism) complemented the other.

Proof of the above is the fact that the Jews inhabiting Thessaloniki and surrounding towns and regions during the Roman period and beyond are called Romaniotes. The term defines Jews that have partly incorporated Greek into their religious ceremonies. Epigraphs (monumental inscriptions) on 2 sarcophagi, circa 2nd & 3^d Century CE, attest to that and prove the Jewish presence⁵. Also, an important find was the column from the ancient synagogue at Stobi (Οι Στόβοι), just 100 klms away, with the inscription in Greek referring to “*Polycharmos, Father of the Synagogue*”.⁶

Saul of Tarsus, a pious Jew, better known in the Christian World as Apostle Paul, the founder of Christianity as a religion – religious creed – based on the belief of the Deity of Jesus of Nazareth, preached for 3 consecutive weeks at the Ets Ahaim synagogue to native Jews in Thessaloniki in 50 CE. He wasn't very convincing: the crowd showed feelings of hostility, and he had to be spirited away towards the city of Veria⁷. It is interesting to note that

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- 55 Pantelis Nigdelis, *Επιγραφικά Θεσσαλονίκεια: Συμβολή στην πολιτική και κοινωνική ιστορία της αρχαίας Θεσσαλονίκης _ Thessaloniki Inscriptions: Contribution to the social history of Ancient Thessaloniki* (in Greek), University Studio Press, 646 pages, Thessaloniki, 2006
- Pantelis M. Nigdelis, *Synagoge(n) und Gemeinde der Juden in Thessalonika: Fragen aufgrund einer neuen jüdischen Grabinschrift der Kaiserzeit*, *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*, 102, pp 297-307, 1994
https://www.academia.edu/13047014/Synagoge_n_und_Gemeinde_der_Juden_in_Thessaloniki_Fragen_aufgrund_einer_neuen_j%C3%BCdischen_Grabinschrift_der_Kaiserzeit_ZPE_102_1994_297-306
- 6 Ephrat Habas (Rubin), *The Dedication of Polycharmos from Stobi: Problems of Dating and Interpretation*, *The Jewish Quarterly Review*, New Series, Vol. 92, No. 1/2, pp. 41-78, Jul. - Oct., 2001
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTbDhENVpCT3pzMDg/view?usp=sharing>
- N. Vulic, *Inscription grecque de Stobi*, *Bulletin de correspondance hellénique*, Volume 56, pp. 291-298, 1932 (20170922)
http://www.persee.fr/web/revues/home/prescript/article/bch_0007-4217_1932_num_56_1_2840
- JAMES WISEMAN, *JEWS AT STOBI*, [James Wiseman, Židovi u Stobima], Kačić, Split, 2009.-2011., 41-43, pp. 325-350, *Izvorni znanstveni članak*, pp. 325-350, Priljeno: 28. III. 2011
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTNFM2SVI0S1FoNGs/view?usp=sharing>
- 7 PHILANDER, *THE NOBLE BEREANS, AND IGNOBLE THESSALONIANS*, *The Massachusetts Missionary Magazine*, Containing Religious and Interesting C..., 5, 12, pg. 466, May 1808

Professor Dimitrios Kyrtatas states that the first Christians in Macedonia were, in most of the cases, either Hellenized Jews or Hellenized Jewish sympathizers⁸.

For the period up to the creation of the Eastern Roman Empire, known as Byzantium, it is safe to assume that Jews were left to live their lives without any religious discrimination. That was so since both the Hellenic God Pantheon and the Roman one did not relate to other religions. The exemptions had to do with the political aims of various conquerors of Jerusalem who saw in Jews a nation, potentially hostile, and not a religion.

It is with the Roman Emperor Flavius Valerius Aurelius Constantinus Augustus, also known in the Greek Christian Orthodox Church as Constantine the Great or Saint Constantine, that the fortunes of, both, Thessaloniki and its Jews were inexorably linked with the fortunes or misfortunes and policies of Byzantium. Constantine converted to Christianity and, with the Edict of Milan in 313 CE, he granted religious liberty to Christians and to other religions. However, incrementally the Christian Religion became the de facto state religion and, finally, under Emperor Theodosius I, the state Church of the Roman Empire was established (de jure) with the Edict of Thessaloniki, on February 27, 380.⁹

The implications of these were monumental, especially for the Jews: Eastern Orthodox Christianity became the sole authorized religion–creed of the Empire. For the first time in History State and Religion coincide and are merged into one. Religion is being used for political aims. The Ecumenical Patriarch is there; however, in all things that involve Eastern Christianity and/or in the name of it, the Emperor is the bearer of all responsibilities emanating from this usurpation of spiritual power by the worldly one. It is in this respect that the Emperor is the sole institution

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTbUl5TnZHc1V5TzQ/view?usp=sharing>

⁸ Dimitris Kyrtatas, ed. Robin J. Lane Fox, *Early Christianity in Macedonia*, in *Brill's Companion to Ancient Macedon: Studies in the Archaeology and History of Macedon*, 650 BC-300 AD, pp. 585-599, Brill, Leiden – Boston, 2011

⁹ Robert L. Wilken, *The Jews and Christian Apologetics after Theodosius I Cunctos Populos*, *The Harvard Theological Review*, Vol. 73, No. 3/4 (Jul. - Oct., 1980), pp. 451-471, Cambridge University Press on behalf of the Harvard Divinity School, 1980

Dragoş BOICU, *Le pluralisme religieux par la perspective de la législation théodosien publié dans l'intervalle 381-387*, *Revista Teologica*, Vol. 23 Issue 2, pp. 85-102, apr-iun 2013 (in French)

accountable for periodic discrimination and persecution of Jews, various Anti-Judaic edicts and others¹⁰, all in the spirit of the superiority and complete dominance of Christianity in the Empire. This is the complete opposite of Catholic Europe where the Pope held both spiritual and temporal powers and, thus, almost all atrocities committed in the name of Christianity, in the realm of Catholicism, can be attributed to him (the Pope)¹¹.

The Emperor believed that he could use a State Religion as the unifying force and catalyst for the vast empire that comprised many people in order to govern it efficiently and reign on them. The effects of equating a nation with a religion were and are catalytic, long after the dissolution of the Byzantine Empire and, even, today. It is in the Balkans especially, an important geographic region of the Empire for reasons of commerce, expanse, proximity with western Europe, where, definitely, even today, a religion identifies an ethnicity and not vice versa! The Jews of Thessaloniki, and not only, suffered from that.

The Jewish presence in Thessaloniki is sparingly recorded in those years: There is a mention of Rabbi Tobias Ben Eliezer¹² who, circa 1096, wrote his book, *Midrash Lekah Tov* [“Good Doctrine” – a commentary of the Pentateuch]. In it he also attacks the Karaites. In 1170, Benjamin of Tudela¹³ visits the city and reports that the

¹⁰ Nicholas de Lange, *Hebraism and Hellenism: The Case of Byzantine Jewry*, *Poetics Today*, Vol. 19, No. 1, Hellenism and Hebraism Reconsidered: The Poetics of Cultural Influence and Exchange I, pp. 129-145, Duke University Press, Spring 1998

¹¹ (just to get an idea) David I. Kertzer, *The kidnapping of Edgardo Mortara*, 261 pages, Vintage Books, New York, 1998

¹² John Van Antwerp Fine Jr, *The Late Medieval Balkans: A Critical Survey from the Late Twelfth Century to the Ottoman Conquest*, University of Michigan Press, 683 pages, Ann Arbor, 1994
See The Jews in the Balkans, pp. 446-452

Michael Molho, *Histoire des Israélites de Castoria*, 138 pages, Thessaloniki, 1938 (in French) For Tobias Ben Eliezer after page 9 (20170922)

http://www.rachelnet.net/media/aiu/livres/FR_AIU_L_U188.pdf

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTY1pvdXV2cm01Q28/view?usp=sharing>

¹³ Asher A. Editor & Translator, *The Itinerary of Rabbi Benjamin of Tudela, Vol. I*, A. Asher & Co., 165 pages in English, London & Berlin, 1840

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTZ3BSaC1oVVhIbHM/view?usp=sharing>
THE TRAVELS OF RABBI BENJAMIN OF TUDELA, *The University magazine*
1878-1880, pp. 598-612, Nov 1878

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTc0NqN0xZenUzeTA/view?usp=sharing>

Jews are oppressed. And Archbishop Eustathios¹⁴, in his account of the Norman Siege and *Capture of Thessaloniki* in 1185, is not kind to the Jews.

This should not come as a surprise: Emperors Constantine I, Theodosius II, and Justinian I among others adhered to an Anti-Judaic comportment: Constantine claimed that the Jews are unclean, and the other 2 passed Anti-Judaic legislation, Theodosius in his Codex Theodosianus¹⁵ and Justinian in his [Novella 146 on Jews](#)¹⁶. Later Emperors are also attributed with various similar acts and comportment. All of these restrictive measures applied equally to the Jews of Thessaloniki, a city second only to Constantinople in importance in Byzantium. Thus, it is almost certain that Byzantine Administration was, if not outright hostile, at the least not friendly towards the Jews. Besides, (Emperor) Constantine's speeches, as recorded by Eusebius Bishop of Caesarea¹⁷ and Theodoret of Cyrus¹⁸ corroborate the above.

¹⁴ John R. Melville-Jones, *Eustathius (Archbishop of Thessalonica)*, Australian Association for Byzantine Studies, *Byzantina Australiensia* 8, 244 pages, Canberra, 1988

See the Power Point Presentation

ΕΥΣΤΑΘΙΟΥ ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ – ΙΣΤΟΡΙΚΟΝ ΤΗΣ ΑΛΩΣΕΩΣ ΤΗΣ ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ
Efstathios of Thessaloniki – *Record of the Fall of Thessaloniki* (in Greek) (20170317)
http://users.uoa.gr/~nektar/history/2romanity/eysta8ios_8essalonikh_capture.htm

¹⁵ This Day in Jewish History, David B. Green, *The Theodosian Code Is Published Spelling Bad News for Jews*, Haaretz, Jan 31, 2013 9:41 AM

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTbEU30FZLME51cW8/view?usp=sharing>

¹⁶ Corpus Juris Civilis Novellae part 3 _page 641 Nov 146_CXLVI

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTbXE0anBhaV9aM1k/view?usp=sharing>

¹⁷ *Eusebius (Bishop of Caesarea) Life of Constantine*, Introduction, Translation and Commentary by Averil Cameron and Stuart G. Hall, Oxford University Press, 414 pages Oxford, 1999

(for Greek Speakers)

Vita Constantini – *Εἰς τὸν βίον Κωνσταντίνου, ΚΕΦΑΛΑΙΑ ΤΟΥ ΚΑΤΑ ΘΕΟΝ ΒΙΟΥ ΤΟΥ ΜΑΚΑΡΙΟΥ ΚΩΝΣΤΑΝΤΙΝΟΥ ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ*, Ερευνητικό Έργο: Δρόμοι της Πίστης Χριστιανική Πατρολογία, Εργαστήριο Διαχείρισης Πολιτισμικής Κληρονομιάς, www.aegean.gr/culturaltec/chmlab, Πανεπιστήμιο Αιγαίου, Τμήμα Πολιτισμικής Τεχνολογίας και Επικοινωνίας, 2006 (20170325)

https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=oahUKEwi6xpnN5d_SAhUCXRoKHRI7CysQFggYMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fkhazarzar.skeptik.net%2Fpgm%2FPG_Migne%2FEusebius%2520Caesariensis_PG%252019-24%2FVita%2520Constantini.pdf&usq=AFQjCNGwN4bRMKObXDBM2jLXs22k9TkBYg&sig2=hf8_MSQsCPESPRNZG9lynw&bvm=bv.150120842.d.d2s

¹⁸ Theodoret of Cyrus, *Historia Ecclesiastica* (20170924)

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http://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/03d/0393-0457.Theodoretus.Historia_Ecclesiastica_EN.pdf

Venetian Rule of the city occurs the years 1423–1430. Jewish immigration from Italy and Sicily takes place adding to other arrivals such as, in 1376, Jews from Hungary and Germany. In the meantime, the decline of Byzantium is irreversible. The city will not revert to its rule but will be conquered by the Ottoman (Osmanlı) Empire on March 29, 1430. After Constantinople also fell (1453), Jews inhabiting İstanbul are allowed to migrate in other cities and these include Thessaloniki. Note that the White Tower is built on the onset of Ottoman rule.

At the same time, Sephardic Judaism is thriving in the Iberian Peninsula, in Spain and Portugal. Regrettably, however, Christian Spain under the Catholic Kings Ferdinand II of Aragon and Isabella I of Castile decided that all Jews who did not convert to Christianity had to leave. Their decision was formalized with the Alhambra Decree – the [Edict of Expulsion](#)¹⁹– issued on 31 March 1492²⁰. It ordered the expulsion of Jews, who declined to convert, from the Crowns [Kingdoms] of Castile and Aragon and its territories and possessions by the 31st July of that year²¹.

(for Greek Speakers)

Historia ecclesiastica, *Τάδε ἔνεστιν ἐν τῷ πρώτῳ τόμῳ τῆς Θεοδωρήτου ἐκκλησιαστικῆς ἱστορίας*, Ερευνητικό Έργο: Δρόμοι της Πίστης Χριστιανική Πατρολογία, Εργαστήριο Διαχείρισης Πολιτισμικής Κληρονομιάς, www.aegean.gr/culturaltec/chmlab, Πανεπιστήμιο Αιγαίου, Τμήμα Πολιτισμικής Τεχνολογίας και Επικοινωνίας, 2006 (20170325)
https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=oahUKEwj30Zn-49_SAhWGiRoKHd7iAyoQFggaMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fkhazarzar.skeptik.net%2Fpgm%2FPG_Migne%2FTheodoretus%2520of%2520Cyrillus_PG%252080-84%2FHistoria%2520ecclesiastica.pdf&usq=AFQjCNGQ4A7IFjgcfVL9O10gYJoSOr6WBw&sig2=zZX1BPtVXemIU2DofEQRWQ

¹⁹ http://www.redjuderias.org/google/google_maps_imgs/avila/expulsion01.jpg

²⁰ Edward Peters, *Jewish History and Gentile Memory: The Expulsion of 1492*, *Jewish History*, Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 9–34, Spring 1995
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTVV9MRkFvTTNDbjA/view?usp=sharing>

²¹ The 3rd Sephardic Heritage World Summit Conference [**Cumbre Erensyá Sefardí**] took place in Spain in spring 2015. My wife Nelly and I took part. We made an effort to converse only in Judeo–Español. We visited Ávila where we saw the original edict of expulsion (many were reproduced by hand writing in order to forward them to various localities throughout the Catholic kingdoms). It had been 523 years since the expulsion and we were back where it all had begun. Now, this time around, on Wednesday, April 29, 2015, we were received by **His Majesty the King of Spain Don Felipe VI** [*Felipe Juan Pablo Alfonso de Todos los Santos de Borbón y Grecia*]. It was an overwhelming experience and the sentiments too strong to describe. He thanked me in Greek for my presence. Nonetheless the

Sultân Bayezid-î Velî (II) welcomed them in the Empire. Around 15000 to 20000 settled in Thessaloniki, Selanik. These Jews brought with them their language, customs and their skills. It was unavoidable that the overwhelming presence of the Spaniards would swallow up the Romaniote minority and erase its traces from the city²².

Jewish Thessaloniki is now part of a vast Empire. It will remain so up to 1912. Jews in Thessaloniki are treated the same as in other parts and, specifically, as their coreligionists in many Jewish centers such İstanbul and İzmir. As during the Byzantine era, Thessaloniki is second to the capital İstanbul. Jews enjoy the same privileges and are subject to the same rules and obligations like the Christians. These sprang from the concept of dhimmî (Zimmî), as non-Muslim citizens of an Islamic State. Coupled to that, Jews belonged to the Jewish Millet, or, loosely defined, religious minority community. The Sublime Porte believed that the best way to govern the Empire, given the large non-Muslim population aggregations that were present was to a) give some autonomy on linguistic, religious and social issues in the non-Muslim communities and b) populate various geographic areas with Muslim Turks and/or encourage conversion of local populations. In this respect the Ottoman Empire differed from Byzantium.

Thus the Jews of Thessaloniki are Ottoman subjects but not first class citizens. However, due to this system of governance, a positive outcome is that the spirit of communality among the Jews and that of taking care of their own was reinforced. Furthermore, very few Jews ever learned Turkish, the language of the Administration and the majority. This created the need, and, simultaneously, employment opportunities, for a stratum – branch of midlevel state employees mediating between the administration and the non-Muslim citizens.

Again there is an influx of various Jewish groups during the 16th and 17th centuries, coming from all over: from Portugal, after they have been expelled as in Spain, from Poland, Hungary, Italy and

clock cannot turn back. (20170924)

http://www.sefarad-israel.es/tercera_cumbre_erehsya_centro_sefarad_israel

²² MICHAEL MOLHO, *Usos y costumbres de los judíos de Salónica*, *Sefarad*, 7:1, pp. 93-121, 1947

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTRVIZalV0QWlqaGc/view?usp=sharing>

North Africa. The dominant Sephardic element prevailed over all newcomers, Sephardic or otherwise. And, in 1545 (5305), the Portuguese Marrano Samuel Usque²³ will characterize it as the “Mother of Judaism” in his opus *Consolation for the Tribulations of Israel*. Cultural growth along with economic growth will last until the beginning of the 17th Century. However, later, new sea routes as well as the involvement of the Ottoman Empire in military campaigns will bring economic malaise and cultural decline.

That is why, the appearance of Sabbetai Sevy and his acceptance by many Jews of Thessaloniki as the Messiah should come as no surprise. Originating from İzmir, he declared himself the Messiah. The result for Thessaloniki was the splitting of the community to believers and non-believers. When the Ottoman authorities forced him to convert to Islam in 1666, a few hundred families followed him into conversion and thus created the complex minority of «Judeo-Muslims», or Dönme [«Turncoats»] or, as they prefer to be called, the «ha-Ma’aminim» i.e. The Believers. Nominally, they were considered Muslims. The Yeni Camii, built in 1902, served as their temple up to 1923 when, with the Treaty of Lausanne, they were forcibly expelled to Turkey as Muslims²⁴.

Fast forwarding to the 19th Century: Noteworthy milestones are the publishing, in 1864, of the first Judeo-Spanish newspaper *El Lunar* and, in 1873, the establishment of schools by the *Alliance Israélite Universelle*.^{25 26} But we find the Empire with many

²³ Samuel Usque, *Consolação às Tribulações de Israel 1*, França Amado Editor, Coimbra, pp. 502, 1553, 1906

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTdVgtWXD1eTdkYW8/view?usp=sharing>

Isis Carolina Garcia Bispo, *Consolação às Tribulações de Israel: Um documento textual para preservação da memória dos Sefarditas*, *Anais do III Seminário Nacional Literariae Cultura* (SENALIC), 12 pages, São Cristovão, 2011

https://www.academia.edu/4495821/Consola%C3%A7%C3%A3o_%C3%A0s_Tribula%C3%A7%C3%B5es_de_Israel_um_documento_textual_para_a_preserva%C3%A7%C3%A3o_da_mem%C3%B3ria_dos_Sefarditas (20170924)

²⁴ *A Strange Sect in Saloniki*, *New York Times*, page 71, Jan 26, 1919

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTb1BNRWxoeE9YZVk/view?usp=sharing>

²⁵ <http://www.aiu.org/en/archives-o>

²⁶ *Further correspondence respecting the affairs of Turkey*, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons, [C.1738] Turkey No. 15 (1877), page 321(303), 374 pages, London, 1877 (see page 321)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTYjFZZHZGSIVWOGM/view?usp=sharing>

internal and external issues and problems: Tanzimat²⁷, in 1839, and the Hatt-ı Hümayun^{28 29} of 1856³⁰, both from Sultan Abdülmecid, as well as various other measures over the years were both a bit late and little in order to stem the national aspirations of the subjects of different religion and language, especially of the Christian ones. That was the unintended result of the Ottoman model of Administration, efficient for the first centuries but woefully inadequate for the later modern ones³¹. It was too late to both promote and forge the notion of the Ottoman Citizen based on full Civil rights and not institutionalized incomplete minority group rights. One outcome of the long presence of the Ottomans in the Balkans was the reinforcement of the identification and/or equation of a particular ethnic/national group with a certain language and religion, even a particular Patriarchate. That was due to their mode of government. This holds true even today! Only Jews were a non-ethnic religious group. So, in the 1st Balkan War we find Thessaloniki inhabited by Greeks [Orthodox Christians], Turks [Muslims], Bulgarians [Orthodox Christians of the Exarchate], Serbians [Orthodox Christians], Jews and a few other minor groups.

²⁷ *Correspondence respecting the condition of Protestants in Turkey 1841-1851*. Presented to the House of Commons in pursuance of their Address of March 27, 1851, House of Commons [1392], 110 pages, page 20, London, 1851

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTSVZaSkZWN2FHMEk/view?usp=sharing>

²⁸ *Firman and Hatti-Sherif by the Sultan, relative to privileges and reforms in Turkey*, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons, [2040] Part XVII, Eastern papers, 10 pages London, 1856

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTVGtSSDZiWGdoaTA/view?usp=sharing>

²⁹ *Reports received from Her Majesty's consuls relating to the condition of Christians in Turkey*, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons, [2884], 99 pages, London, 1861 page 9 Thessaloniki, page 13 Mamin (Dönme)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTcjhyaElfdW5Bb2c/view?usp=sharing>

³⁰ *Part II. Reports received from Her Majesty's consuls relating to the condition of Christians in Turkey*, Presented to the House of Commons by Command of Her Majesty in pursuance of their Address of March 6, 1867, House of Commons, [3854] [3944] Part II, 100 pages, London, 1867

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTS1dVZHhoZENMOEU/view?usp=sharing>

³¹ *Correspondence respecting the new law for the European provinces of Turkey*, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons, [C.2703] [C.2703-I] Turkey No. 15 (1880) Part I, 300 pages, page 20, London, 1880

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTeFBwOWxmNXUzVjA/view?usp=sharing>

The Greek Army enters Thessaloniki on October 26, 1912. In 1913, with the Treaty of Bucharest³², the city becomes officially Greek. And, with the Treaty of Athens in 1913, a Treaty of Peace between Greece and Turkey, the Greek citizenship is acquired by all, Christians, Muslims, and Jews³³. Bear in mind that the Hellenic State, officially founded in 1830 with the Treaties of London³⁴, in

³² *ΣΥΝΘΗΚΗ ΕΙΡΗΝΗΣ ΒΟΥΚΟΥΡΕΣΤΙΟΥ (10 ΑΥΓΟΥΣΤΟΥ 1913) μεταξύ Ελλάδας, Ρουμανίας, Μαυροβουνίου, Σερβίας, Βουλγαρίας, Εφημερίς της Κυβερνήσεως του Βασιλείου της Ελλάδας*, ΦΕΚ Α' 217/28 ΟΚΤΩΒΡΙΟΥ 1913 *TREATY OF PEACE OF BUCHAREST (10 August 1913) between Greece, Romania, Montenegro, Serbia, & Bulgaria, Government Gazette of the Kingdom of Greece*, Series FEK A' 217/28 October 1913 (In Greek and French)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTVoQ2UU5NMnVTdUk/view?usp=sharing>
Minutes and Protocols (in French) of the Peace Conference in Bucharest from July 28 till August 10, 1913 (start from page 19 of the document attached)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTYos2MDVtaWNWbHM/view?usp=sharing>

³³ *Κύρωση της Συνθήκης Ειρήνης (Ελληνικά & Γαλλικά), Εφημερίς της Κυβερνήσεως του Βασιλείου της Ελλάδας*, Τεύχος Α, Αριθμός 229 14 Νοεμβρίου 1913, Αθήνα, www.et.gr [Σημείωση: Είναι η Συνθήκη των Αθηνών του 1913] *Ratification of the Peace Treaty (in Greek & French), Government Gazette of the Kingdom of Greece*, Issue Series A', Number 229 November 14, 1913, Athens, www.et.gr, [Note: this is the Treaty of Athens of 1913]

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTTVdCQlg4Voc4UG8/view?usp=sharing>

³⁴ *A _ Papers relative to the Affairs of Greece, Protocols of Conferences Held in London*, House of Commons, 1830, 340 σελίδες, London
σελίδα 316

The London Conferences 1830 No. 25.

PROTOCOL, No. 3, of the Conference held at the Foreign Office on the 3rd of February, 1830.

Present: The Plenipotentiaries of Great Britain; France; and Russia.

...

The Plenipotentiaries of Great Britain and Russia appreciated the justice of this demand; and it was decided that the Catholic religion should enjoy in the new State the free and public exercise of its worship, that its property should be guaranteed to it, that its bishops should be maintained in the integrity of the functions, rights, and privileges, which they have enjoyed under the protection of the Kings of France, and that, lastly, agreeably to the same principle, the properties belonging to the ancient French Missions, or French Establishments, shall be recognized and respected.

The Plenipotentiaries of the three Allied Courts being desirous moreover of giving to Greece a new proof of the benevolent anxiety of their Sovereigns respecting it, and of preserving that country from the calamities which the rivalry of the religions therein professed might excite, agreed that all the subjects of the new State, whatever may be their religion, shall be admissible to all public employments, functions, and honours, and be treated on the footing of a perfect equality, without regard to difference of creed, in all their relations, religious, civil, or political.

...

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB6Vpuw9GQ6A5VmZ1Smw3MnpyN2M/view?usp=sharing>

In January 1st 1822, the First National Assembly met at Epidaurus and ratified the First Constitution of Greece. It is with this Constitution that the Greek Nation acquires its first statehood. For the *Temporary System of Government* see (in Greek):

all its constitutions proclaimed not only full freedom of religion but also full emancipation. They [Constitutions] were based on Civil rights and not group rights. No minorities were recognized. Every person was a Hellene.

After more than 2000 years the Jew of Thessaloniki becomes, by Constitutional mandate, a Greek, albeit of Jewish religious decent. It was predictable that the Constitutional mandate for de jure incorporation into the national corpus could not be transubstantiated into a de facto one overnight. For that, the time span of at least a few generations was needed and, also, the resolve of the state, to encourage the process through education and other means, was requisite and essential.

Unfortunately, Greece was confronted with many issues, not all troubles free, during that period: The First World War, its [Greece] territorial expansion in the Balkans, and its [Greece] presence in Asia Minor in Smyrna after 1919. At the time, modern nationalistic³⁵ Turkey under Mustafa Kemal Atatürk was ascertaining itself. The over extension of Greek forces in Asia Minor resulted in defeat and they were forced to abandon all territories. With the Peace Treaty of Lausanne in 1923³⁶, the first and only ever forced population exchange between two states,

<http://www.hellenicparliament.gr/UserFiles/f3c70a23-7696-49db-9148-f24dce6a27c8/syno6.pdf>

³⁵ The only sure defense mechanism left for the disintegrating Ottoman Empire was to revert from an inclusive Empire to an exclusive Nation State exactly like the ones that were severed from its corpus. The fuse of the catalyst for this irrevocable process: The Greek National Revolt against the Ottomans in 1821.

³⁶ *Treaty of peace with Turkey, and other instruments signed at Lausanne on July 24, 1923, together with agreements between Greece and Turkey signed on January 30, 1923, and subsidiary documents forming part of the Turkish Peace Settlement [With map]*, Presented to the Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [Cmd. 1929] Treaty Series No. 16 (1923), 250 pages, London, 1923

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTcHFWeTJMYzM1Rok/view?usp=sharing>

Records of proceedings of the Lausanne Conference on Near Eastern Affairs, 1922-23, with draft terms of Peace. (Lausanne Conference: GENERAL Turkey (Lausanne)), Presented to the Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [Cmd. 1814] Turkey No. 1 (1923), 883 pages, London, 1923

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTcjBaN3JKZEljVoo/view?usp=sharing>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTQS1VcHdKTGFenM/view?usp=sharing>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTN29uWmtmWXVWSUo/view?usp=sharing>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTVnV4eVZHSExtcok/view?usp=sharing>

based solely on religion, took place. The Dönme were transplanted to Turkey along with other Muslims either ethnic or non-ethnic Turks. Also, in 1917, a major fire swept the predominantly Jewish city center of Thessaloniki· the subsequent urban planning altered forever its centuries old Jewish–Ottoman character.

The majority of the Christians – Rum, Ethnic Greeks, Ionians, Yavan settled in Macedonia and, many out of those, in Thessaloniki. This altered irrevocably the population distribution and statistics. Thessaloniki still had the largest Sephardic community but it would never again regain its status as a Jewish City, Mother in Israel. Whereas before the Jewish element dominated commerce, now it had to compete against the Christian Hellenic majority when still most Jews spoke Judeo– Español³⁷ (Ladino) and not Greek. Everyone's economic realm was curtailed by the new borders and the multitude of new nation–states in Europe.

Jewish communities were recognized as public legal entities with Law 2456/1920 on *Israelite* (Jewish) Communities³⁸. The Jewish Community of Thessaloniki was formally created and received its Bylaws with a decree published in 1923³⁹. The community diminished in population reaching a total of around 55000 on the eve of the Second World War. The majority lead a hand to mouth existence even though many tend to equate or believe the urban legend that most were rich. There existed some rich ones but this was not the case for the overwhelming majority.

³⁷ Max Leopold Wagner, *Beiträge zur Kenntnis des Judenspanischen von Konstantinopel. Mit 1 Schrifttafel und 3 Abbildungen im Texte*, Kaiserliche Akademie der Wissenschaften, Schriften der Balkankommission, Linguistische Abteilung 11, 110 pages, Hölder, Wien, 1914

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTS01jZUxobEZxNkU/view?usp=sharing>

³⁸ Νόμος 2456, *Περί Ισραηλιτικών Κοινοτήτων*, *Εφημερίς της Κυβερνήσεως του Βασιλείου της Ελλάδος*, Τεύχος 1ον, Αριθμός Φύλλου 173, 2 Αυγούστου 1920 Law 2456, *Regarding Jewish Communities*, *Government Gazette of the Kingdom of Greece*, Series Issue 1st, Number Issue 173, August 2, 1920 (in Greek)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTVHMyejRPeopKWDA/view?usp=sharing>

³⁹ The download URLs for the A. the original **Bylaws** [Καταστατικό] as published in the Government Gazette of 1923 and obtained by the National Printing Office [www.et.gr] and, B. the codified Bylaws with all subsequent amendments as it is valid today (all in Greek)

A. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTVoVLdzV2eVVKMHM/view?usp=sharing>

B. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTbUthclU1YlhSSIU/view?usp=sharing>

The inter war years shaped the community in various respects: Hellenization compelled the new generation to learn and speak Greek even though instruction in French and the learning of Ladino continued. However, incorporation and social mingling for the many with the Christian majority did not advance at a desirable pace due to the large numbers of Jews and the gap of generations – the older generations continued to speak Ladino⁴⁰ –. The Communal benevolent services catered to the needy. Synagogues functioned as well as religious schools. There were some acts of outright Anti–Semitism but it was neither

⁴⁰ Today Judeo Español is officially recognized in the European Union as one of the severely endangered languages:

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, WORKING PAPER, *The European Union and Lesser-used Languages*, Education and Culture Series, EDUC 108 EN, Luxembourg, European Parliament, July 2002

[https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=oahUKEwjZ9MPVpeDSAhWDHxoKHYVTCyoQFggaMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.europarl.europa.eu%2FRegData%2Fetudes%2Fdocument_travail%2Feduc%2F2002%2Fo108%2Fo4A-EDUC_DT\(2002\)0108_EN.doc&usq=AFQjCNFSixKbA94Rb7UOVs8nCe_gc0f2bg&sig2=-iguZekhIaW-TO95LrqHHA](https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=oahUKEwjZ9MPVpeDSAhWDHxoKHYVTCyoQFggaMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.europarl.europa.eu%2FRegData%2Fetudes%2Fdocument_travail%2Feduc%2F2002%2Fo108%2Fo4A-EDUC_DT(2002)0108_EN.doc&usq=AFQjCNFSixKbA94Rb7UOVs8nCe_gc0f2bg&sig2=-iguZekhIaW-TO95LrqHHA)

see Judeo-Spanish

<http://www.unesco.org/languages-atlas/en/atlasmap/language-iso-lad.html>Ladino

Judezmo (Europe) in Unesco Languages

Variant(s): Judeo-Spanish, Judezmo, Dzhudezmo, Haketía

Also: **Ladino**; **Judeo-Spanish**; Sephardic; Haketía (local name in Morocco)

Judezmo (Europe) (en), judéo-espagnol (Europe) (fr), sefardí (Europa) (es), сефардский (ru)

Geographical location: since the Middle Ages, in dispersed communities mainly & traditionally Greece and Turkey, primarily in the historical provinces of Macedonia and Thrace, but also elsewhere in the Balkans, as well as Morocco, Ceuta, Melilla and Algeria in North Africa, and Israel; now a few locations in Turkey, where largely concentrated in Istanbul (traditionally in the quarters of Balat and Hasköy), by probably less than 10,000 speakers; in Greece or elsewhere in the Balkans there are very few if any Judezmo speakers left after the Holocaust, and in North Africa the language is extinct

the traditional language of Sephardic Jews

Relationships: a Jewish Ibero-Romance language

Present state of the language: SEVERELY ENDANGERED

(a) children speakers: probably few if any

(b) mean age of youngest speakers: not known

(c) distribution by sex:

(d) total number of speakers, members of the ethnic group: 8,000 speakers estimated in Turkey (1980); very few if any in Greece or elsewhere in the Balkans or in Morocco; perhaps as many as 100,000 in Israel, but Ladino is not the dominant language for most speakers; speakers are generally over 40 years old

(e) degree of speakers' competence: probably quite few fully competent speakers

Remarks: the traditional language of Sephardic Jews

Haïm V. Séphiha, *Le judéo-espagnol*, 241 pages, Paris, 1986

Saving the Judaeo-Spanish Language and Culture

<http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php>

[URL_ID=4311&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html](http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php)

institutionalized nor state sanction or promoted⁴¹. After the Campbell mini-pogrom in 1931, many immigrated to Palestine, even though immigration to both Palestine and elsewhere had started before and continued after.

The darkest period (and page) of our History is approaching fast: World War II has commenced. The Italians attack and attempt to invade Greece on the Albanian front in the 28th of October 1940. The Greek Army dealt them decisive blows, pushes them back and is victorious in the field – more than 11000 Jewish Greek soldiers and officers take part in the Campaign –. Their German Axis Allies come to their rescue. The Deutsches [German] Reich attacks and invades Greece on April 6, 1941. Thessaloniki is occupied on April 9th. The annihilation of the Jewish Greek population of Thessaloniki, that came as a result of the implementation of the so-called Final Solution of the Jewish Problem by the German Reich⁴² and the waste and ruins that it left on its wake, is one of the most infamous events in World History^{43 44}.

⁴¹ It is worth (in my opinion) to research the reason(s) why the Statesman **Eleftherios Venizelos** had a negative obsession with the Jews. I am just stating it as a historical fact that should be taken into account in a more detailed historiography of the Jewish Greeks, mainly of Thessaloniki but also of the whole of Greece, during the interwar years.

⁴² Archival Document
title: *Deportations of Jews from Greece to Auschwitz. A Statistical Survey. The 'Final Solution' (September 1939-1945): Concentration Camps: Alphabetical Order. Eyewitness Accounts*
source: [Archives of the Wiener Library](#), London
Author: Smolen, Kazimierz (Director of the Auschwitz Museum).
Detail: Document reference number: 054-EA-0997. P.III.h. No.958. (Auschwitz); 20 March 1943 to 25 May 1944. 8 pages, 1958

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTWnRvNmFOV2lnX28/view?usp=sharing>

⁴³ In December of 1942 the centuries old Jewish Cemetery of Thessaloniki was destroyed (a historically relevant article follows)
Michael Molho, *El cementerio judío de Salónica*, *Sefarad*, 9:1, pp.107-130, 1949

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTVnlkOFJXeF9qNzg/view?usp=sharing>

⁴⁴ Anders Rydell (Author), Henning Koch (Translator), *The Book Thieves: The Nazi Looting of Europe's Libraries and the Race to Return a Literary Inheritance*, 277 pages, Viking – Penguin Random House, New York, February 7, 2017
Κεφάλαιο 10, **Fragments of a People, Thessaloniki**, pages 134 -144
(note: I was interviewed by the Author in Thessaloniki)

The numeric strength of the community, just before deportations started in March 15, 1943, is deduced from a [document](#),⁴⁵ signed by **SS Hauptsturmführer Dieter Wisliceny** which authorizes the release of cardboard for the printing of **Jewish Identity Cards**, where the **Jewish Greek** population of the city aged 6 and over was estimated at around 55000 souls.

Note: Leon Hagouel fought as a **Greek** but was deported to **Auschwitz - Birkenau** on April 19, 1943 as a **Jew**. He remained incarcerated as a **Häftling**⁴⁶ from April 26, 1943 till January 27, 1945 when he was liberated by Soviet Armed Forces. Liberation day found him in **Auschwitz IV** sub camp or, as it was known, **Blechhammer**. Besides Birkenau, he also got the dubious “privilege” of experiencing the “hospitality” of the notorious **Jaworzno** camp.

It is important to note that the responsibility, if any, of the wartime Kingdom of Italy, first as an aggressor enemy state and then as an occupier, respecting the Holocaust of Jewish Greeks has not been studied and investigated sufficiently⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ From the **personal archive** of **Leon Hagouel**, in my possession, Thessaloniki, 2006 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/OB9Aca9qaK9sTa2pvOXFDengwV2s/view?usp=sharing>
⁴⁶ Konzentrationslager Auschwitz Entry Registration Form Leon Hagouel KL118633 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/OB9Aca9qaK9sTOFFBeVZyakJSRzA/view?usp=sharing>
⁴⁷ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks and Jews of Thessaloniki: Italian truncated and selective Humanity, Spanish adaptable Citizenship [with Update and Addenda & Full Proceedings September 2017]*, Invited Talk and Presentation at the International Scientific Conference “Diplomacy and the

Post war Jewish Thessaloniki is now counting more than 70 years life. Wounds would never heal. Memory and, especially, Remembrance, are taking their revenge. The Community offers again all services for those who wish to lead a full Jewish life. The creation of the State of Israel, as the Jewish State, enhance our consciousness as Jews in Greece but, also, compels us to ascertain even more our Hellenic identity. The challenge is to blossom as Jewish Greeks and not take the “easy way out” of Aliyah – emigration to Israel (or the hard way depending on one’s Weltanschauung!). After all Jewish Greeks fought as equals in all wars and contributed to the glory of the country and the nation.

More subtle are the challenges still emanating from the catastrophe: The maintenance and rebirth of Judeo–Español⁴⁸ as a living language, Judaic Heritage instruction to our youth beyond elementary school – a Jewish Community private elementary school thrives –, resurrection of pre–war customs and maintenance of current ones that disappear as survivors pass away, the passing to new generations of the centuries old recipes, the record of all of the above in written, audio, video electronic form or otherwise, just to name a few.

Last, but most important and not least, the demographic challenge looms ominous: It is the most overwhelming. Vigilance and nurturing of our youth is a must, they have to be proud of our–their heritage and have to be imbued with the conviction of their destiny in keeping Judaism live in Thessaloniki. Already interfaith

Deportation of Jews Southern Balkans in 1943”, Tuesday, January 27, 2015, Skopje at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Co-organizers: Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Skopje, Diplomatic Club – Skopje, Memorial Center of the Holocaust, Skopje, Institute of National History, Skopje, International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance (Berlin Main Office)

Proceedings published late 2016, pp. 67-81 English original, pp. 83-99 Cyrillic (link for full proceedings provided in the pdf text)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTMXdRMFhsNm9XNTg/view?usp=sharing>

or

https://www.academia.edu/34474249/2017_update_The_Holocaust_of_Jewish_Greeks_and_Jews_of_Thessaloniki_Italian_truncated_and_selective_Humanity_Spanish_adaptable_Citizenship_plus_Update_and_Addenda_and_full_Proceedings

⁴⁸ Leire Ventas, *Qué es el ladino, el idioma "en peligro de extinción" al que se quiere dedicar una academia de la RAE para solventar una "deuda histórica"*, *BBC Mundo* (HayFestivalSegovia@BBCMundo), 24 septiembre 2017

<http://www.bbc.com/mundo/noticias-41348482?SThisFB#> or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTaTRVOFJyemNGUVk/view?usp=sharing>

weddings take their toll. It is ironic that complete freedom and full emancipation is neither conducive in strengthening one's root identity nor in keeping the cohesion when a minority.

Personally, I am optimistic that Jewish Thessaloniki will always be present and, hopefully, a contributor to Judaism in the 21st Century and beyond, as well as a catalyst for tolerance, understanding and peace among neighboring nations.

I thank you very much.

Paul Isaac Hagouel
hagouel@eecs.berkeley.edu
paul231011@berkeley.edu
PaulIsaacHagouel.academia.edu
+30 6974389086 cell
+30 2310270886 land

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Power Point Presentation Download Link:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTUWE0ZlI4UkZoaFk/view?usp=sharing>

Power Point Show Download Link:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTREkzejFQZW1waUE/view?usp=sharing>

Film segment [footage] from *Sterne - Stars* Download Link:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTUmh0ck54MGVDSUU/view?usp=sharing> or
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9Aca9qaK9sTa1ZaMUduOThldHc/view?usp=sharing>

Addendum 1

Stars (1959)

The first (and up to very recently forgotten) attempt of “transfer” on film (portrayal, depiction) of the horrific events that took place regarding Jewish Greeks during WWII was the film “*Sterne - Stars*”, an East German [Deutsche Demokratische Republik] & Bulgarian co-production on 1959. It constitutes an important representation of the deportation of Jewish Greeks from the Bulgarian occupied territories of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace of Northern Greece to a transit Concentration Camp inside “old” (main) Bulgaria. Some inexactitudes are insignificant because they do not

change the reality (for example they talk about Auschwitz instead of Treblinka). It is a moving, eloquent, and poignant testament to real events. It is striking that the Jewish Greek teacher, on her way to annihilation, insists on teaching the younger generation - her pupils (who also are on their way to annihilation) the Greek Alphabet. She speaks German to the German non-commissioned officer, Ladino to the elders. We hear talk in Ladino and in Hebrew when an old man recites prayers. The Bulgarian physician talks in his native language. {Watch the characteristic [film segment](#) - footage in German with English subtitles (see download links)}

“*Stars*” uses the narrative of a doomed awkward love attempt to build the plot. We have the German soldier who falls in love with a Jewish Greek internee in a transit Concentration Camp in Bulgaria. The soldier is stationed in a small Bulgarian village, which is adjacent to the camp, in 1943, and he guards the Jews deported from Greece (actually Bulgarians were guarding the Jewish Greeks . . .). The internees-deportees from Greece are on their way to Auschwitz (according to the script) where, supposedly, they will work there in vegetable farms. Clearly, we all know that this is not

true. The same holds true for most of them, but no one wants to admit it.

Some Era -1959- notes: At the time, because the Deutsche Demokratische Republik was not recognized as a state, “*Stars*” was a candidate film at the Cannes Film Festival as the official participation of Bulgaria, instead of the DDR! However, in reality, this was a movie of & from East Germany. It is the only ever German movie that won the **Prix Spécial du Jury du Festival de Cannes** (1959). The irony is that, whereas the movie was popular in East Germany, its screening was prohibited-forbidden in Bulgaria. Why so? My own interpretative conclusion is that it (the movie) showed both a) the perseverance and tenacity of the Jewish Greeks in, stubbornly, abide and adhere to their double heritage that of Sephardic Judaism and Hellenism and, b) the clear role of the Bulgarian authorities of the era not to object to Deportations from Transit Camps on their national territory.

Information:

Sterne (Stars), East Germany - Deutsche Demokratische Republik (DEFA) and Bulgarian Co-Production, black & white, 92 minutes. Feature Director: Konrad Wolf, Script: Angel Raymond Wagenstein (Bulgarian: Анжел Раймонд Вагенщайн) [a Sephardic Jew born in Plovdiv], Dramaturge: Willi Brückner, Camera: Werner Bergmann Editing: Christa Wernicke, Music: Simeon Pironkow, Cast: Jürgen Frohriep (Walter), Sascha Kruscharska (Ruth), Stefan Pejtschew, Erik S. Klein (Kurt), Ivan Kondow (Ruth's father), Stiljan Kunew (the camp doctor). 16mm, English subtitles, 1959.

Languages spoken: Ladino, Greek, Hebrew, German, Bulgarian. Note: Because of the notoriety of *Auschwitz*, in the film they use it instead of the correct destination Extermination Camp of *Treblinka*.

<http://www.imdb.com/title/tt0053306/>

[https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sterne_\(Film\)](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sterne_(Film))

URL links of a characteristic segment [footage] of the film:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/fzzf18rop3oummx/sterne_with_subtrim.avi or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTUmhock54MGVDSUU/view?usp=sharing> or

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB9Aca9qaK9sTa1ZaMUduOThldHc/view?usp=sharing>

Addendum 2

Hellenic Republic

Ministry of Foreign Affairs

Inaugural speech of the Special Secretary for Religious and Cultural Diplomacy, **Dr. Efstathios C. Lianos Liantis**, at the international conference on “The Holocaust: Diachronic and Interdisciplinary Approaches” (Athens, 4 October 2017) & Head of the Greek Delegation to the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance - IHRA

<http://www.mfa.gr/en/current-affairs/news-announcements/inaugural-speech-of-the-special-secretary-for-religious-and-cultural-diplomacy-dr-lianos-liantis-at-the-international-conference-on-the-holocaust-diachronic-and-interdisciplinary-approaches-athens-october-2017.html>

It is highly significant that the Faculty of Social Theology chose to contribute to the celebration of the 180th anniversary of the founding of the National and Kapodistrian University through a conference examining aspects of the Holocaust.

Greek society and the Greek scientific community were late in realising the magnitude of the tragedy of the Holocaust, mainly because of the intensity of developments following the Liberation of 1944 and, in particular, because of the Civil War, which dominated the intellectual and political life of Greece until the founding of the Third Hellenic Republic. Moreover, that time, the early 1980s, saw the writing of the most important literary text about the extermination of the Greek Jews, the short story “In those days ...”, by Giorgos Ioannou.

In 1955, the Jewish German philosopher Theodor Adorno gave us one of the most frequently cited dictums regarding intellectual output and the

Holocaust: “To write poetry after Auschwitz is barbaric.” He thus called into question the use of the intellectual materials of modern Western Civilization, precisely because – as he argued – the Holocaust was not a momentary lapse, but the outcome of a political and cultural process. Some thirty years later, Emil Fackenheim wrote that we cannot comprehend the Holocaust – we can only comprehend its incomprehensibility.

This observation sums up the approach to dealing with the Holocaust through a new *Via Negativa*. Apophatism, or negation, as a theological method of approaching the incomprehensibility of the divine re-emerged in the second half of the 20th century as a philosophical method for examining the identity of the Holocaust. However, in parallel with the philosophical analysis, we also saw the development – among Jews and Christians – of the Theology of the Holocaust. Prominent theologians, clerics and scholars responded to the question of “How could God allow the Holocaust?” and the concomitant question of “How can any faith exist after the Holocaust?”. And herein lies the need for Greek theological schools to study the Shoah and give expression to theological responses based on the eastern tradition. I believe that this conference contributes to this end.

In recent years, Greece has carried out considerable actions concerning remembrance of the Holocaust, a crime, as the Greek Minister of Foreign Affairs recently noted, “unique in history, that concerns the genocide of a people whose only ‘crime’ was their being different from other nations – nations that appeared much later in history.”

Of particular importance is our country’s participation, as a full member, in the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance, the largest global organization bringing together government agencies and experts with the aim of formulating and promoting Holocaust education, remembrance and research; of discussing Holocaust-related issues, including anti-Semitism; and of supporting the commitments of the Stockholm Declaration of 2000.

The IHRA was launched in 1998 – as the Task Force for International Cooperation on Holocaust Education, Remembrance, and Research – by former Swedish Prime Minister Göran Persson. Persson decided to found an international organization that would promote Holocaust education throughout the world, and he asked U.S. President Bill Clinton and British Prime Minister Tony Blair to support this effort. Persson also developed the idea of an international forum for governments interested in discussing Holocaust-related educational actions, and this forum was held in Stockholm from 27 to 29 January 2000. Representatives of 46 governments, including 23 heads of state and 14 deputy prime ministers or ministers, attended this forum. The Declaration of the Stockholm International Forum on the Holocaust resulted from the discussions at the Forum and is the founding document of the IHRA.

The IHRA currently has 31 member countries, 11 observer countries and seven permanent international partners, including the UN and UNESCO. The members commit to the Stockholm Declaration and to the implementation of national policies and programmes supporting Holocaust education, remembrance and research. The government of every member country appoints a delegation to IHRA meetings, made up of government officials and national experts, achieving a productive relationship between the two levels.

It is important to remember that the Holocaust did not begin with executions. It began with rhetoric and moved on to the violation of fundamental rights, culminating in genocide. This is why the IHRA feels such a strong need to combat all forms of hate speech, including anti-Semitism. The Holocaust shows us the potential consequences of policies that deprive people of their fundamental rights and impinge on human dignity.

The Holocaust and Holocaust-related research can teach us a great deal about the role of remembrance, which is so vital today.

Programme

<http://shoah.soctheol.uoa.gr/programme>

School of Theology – Faculty of Social Theology

The Holocaust: Diachronic and Interdisciplinary Approaches

International Conference: 3-5 of October 2017

Part of the Official Celebrations for the 180 years since the founding of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (1837)

Lectures – 3rd of October – Kostis Palamas Building – 19:00-21:00

Inaugural Speeches

The Deputy Chief of Mission of the Embassy of Israel in Athens, Ms. Sawsan Hasson.

The President of the Faculty of Social Theology, Professor Dr. Sotirios Despotis.

The Deputy President of the Faculty of Social Theology, As. Professor Dr. Kirki Kefalea.

Lectures

Dr. Michal Govrin, Writer, Director, Academic Chair of the Theater Department of The Emunah College, To Remember Responsibly: The Holocaust as an Ongoing Ethical Challenge. The Lesson of Jewish Ritual.

Dr. Joel Zisenwine, Project Director at Yad Vashem, Transports to Extinction: Documenting Holocaust Era Deportations.

Inaugural Speeches and 1st Panel – 4th of October – University of Athens Main Building – 10:30-14:00

Inaugural Speeches

The Rector of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Professor Dr. Meletios-Athanasios Demopoulos.

The Special Secretary for Religious and Cultural Diplomacy at the Greek Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Head of the Greek Delegation at IHRA (International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance), Dr. Efstathios C. Lianos Liantis.

The President of the Athens EUNIC (European Union National Institutes of Culture) Cluster, Director of Goethe-Institut Athen and Regional Director of the Goethe-Institutes in Southeastern Europe, Dr. Matthias Makowski.

The Dean of the School of Theology of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Professor Dr. Apostolos Nikolaides.

Sacrifice, subversion and persecution: historical perspectives from the Second

Temple Period / Hellenistic Era until the Middle Ages

Dr. Pablo A. Torijano, Professor at the Department of Hebrew and Aramaic Studies – Complutense University of Madrid, Jewish communities in Late Antiquity: judeophobia and hybrid identity.

Dr. Konstantinos Zarras, Associate Professor at the Faculty of Theology, University of Athens, Job as Israel – Israel as Job in Saadiah Gaon.

Dr. Ioannis Konstantakos, Associate Professor at the Faculty of Philology, University of Athens, Daniel's Holocausts: Persecution and the theological transformation of the Near-Eastern courtly novella.

Anastasia Loudarou, Jewish Museum of Greece Researcher, Archaeologist, M.Sc., Ph.D. candidate in Ancient History, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Judaism in the Graeco-Roman World: A society in conflict? Jews, Samaritans, Greeks and Romans in the island of Delos (2nd c. BCE -1st c. BCE).

Dr. Sotirios Despotis, Professor at the Faculty of Social Theology, University of Athens & Dr. Panagiotis Stamatopoulos, Postdoctoral Research Fellow at the University of Athens, From the Maccabees to Early Christians: the witness as martyr.

Discussion and Free Film Screening – 4th of October – Cultural Centre – 20:30

Free Screening at the Cultural Centre of the City of Athens.

THE INTERROGATION – directed by Erez Pery (2016, Israel – Germany, 84', Greek and English subtitles). Based on the autobiography of Auschwitz commander Rudolf Höss. In 1946, Rudolf Franz Ferdinand Höss, the longest serving commander of Auschwitz concentration camp, is awaiting trial in a Polish prison. Albert, a young and successful Polish investigation judge, is appointed to interrogate Höss and get a perfect confession out of him. The encounter between the two men will unveil the frightening routine and banalization of evil that took place in the camp. By introducing the use of Zyklon B in Auschwitz, Rudolf Höss carried out the most efficient mass killing process ever known, which claimed the lives of approximately 1.1 million people. The film is based on the memoirs Höss wrote before his execution.

The screening is free to the public. With the support of the Organisation for Culture, Youth and Sports of the City of Athens.

2nd Panel – 5th of October – Goethe-Institut – 13:00-15:00

The Holocaust: Historical, Political and Social Approaches with an emphasis on Greece.

Dr. Wolfgang Benz, Professor Emeritus – Technische Universität Berlin, Ideology and the human dimension of experience: The Jews of Rhodes as paradigm.

Dr. Simon Leader, Professor at The American College of Greece, The Holocaust and the Manchester Guardian 1942-43.

Dr. Alexandra Patrikiou, Jewish Museum of Greece Researcher, Individual experiences of hiding places during the Shoah in Greece.

Dr. Leon Saltiel, Postdoctoral Fellow, Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies, Geneva, Efforts in Athens to save the Jews of Thessaloniki during the Holocaust.

Dr. Paul Isaac Hagouel, member of the Academic Working Group of the Greek Delegation to the IHRA and Member of the Committee on the Genocide of the Roma, The Jews of Thessaloniki: Legacies of the Past, Shaping of Traditions, Challenges for the Future.

3rd Panel – 5th of October – Goethe-Institut – 15:30-17:30

A Place and a Name: The Influence of the Holocaust in Literature and the Arts.

Dr. Anca Ciuciu, Associated lecturer of Jewish History at the University of Bucharest and Scientific Secretary at the Centre for the History of Romanian Jewry of the Federation of Jewish Communities in Romania.

Dr. Fragkiski Ampatzopoulou, Professor Emerita at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Philology – Modern Greek Literature, The Holocaust in modern Greek literature.

Dr. Maria Komninou, Professor at the University of Athens – Faculty of Mass Media and Communication, The Holocaust on film.

Dr. Nikolaos Mathioudakis, Academic advisor at Kazantzakis Publications and Professor at the Karolos Koun Drama School, The Holocaust in Theatre.

4th Panel – 5th of October – Goethe-Institut – 18:00-19:30

The Trivialization of Evil and its Implication in Current Debate and Education.

Mr. Andrzej Kacorzuk, ICEAH Director and Deputy Director of the Auschwitz-Birkenau State Museum, Education at the Auschwitz-Birkenau State Museum.

Rabbi Gabriel Negrin, officiating at Beth Shalom Synagogue.

Zanet Battinou, Archaeologist, Director of the Jewish Museum of Greece, Inspiring Active Citizens: The Role of the Jewish Museum of Greece in Holocaust Education.

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HELLENIC REPUBLIC

National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens
School of Theology
Faculty of Social Theology

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An educational action of the postgraduate programme “Theology and Society” of the Faculty of Social Theology – University of Athens

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